

ENCOURAGING STUDENTS TO DO HOMEWORK: CREATIVE APPROACHES FOR EFFECTIVE ENGAGEMENT

Zilola Ochilova

Assistant teacher, Profi University Navoi branch, Navoi, Uzbekistan

Profi universiteti Navoiy filiali o'qituvchisi, Navoiy, O'zbekiston

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Abstract. *This article explores creative approaches to encourage students to complete their homework. It addresses the issue of low motivation among students in Uzbekistan regarding homework and the resulting challenges in fully realizing their academic potential. It discusses how homework can be effectively utilized to reinforce learning and develop students' independent study skills. The author proposes innovative strategies, including personalized assignments, gamification, project-based learning, and technology integration.*

The article serves as a valuable resource for teachers, educational institutions, and parents, providing strategies to enhance student engagement with homework and improve the overall educational experience.

Keywords: *homework, motivation, creative approaches, teaching, student.*

Аннотация. *Эта статья посвящена изучению креативных подходов для мотивации студентов к выполнению домашнего задания. Рассматривается проблема низкой мотивации среди студентов в Узбекистане в отношении домашних заданий и возникающие в результате этого трудности в полном раскрытии их академического потенциала. Обсуждается, как домашние задания могут быть эффективно использованы для укрепления знаний и развития самостоятельных учебных навыков у студентов. Автор предлагает инновационные стратегии, включая персонализированные задания, геймификацию, проектное обучение и интеграцию технологий.*

Статья является ценным ресурсом для учителей, образовательных учреждений и родителей, предлагая стратегии для повышения вовлеченности студентов в выполнение домашних заданий и улучшения общего образовательного опыта.

Ключевые слова: *домашнее задание, мотивация, креативные подходы, обучение, студент.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola o'quvchilarga uy vazifalarini bajarishga rag'batlantirish uchun ijodiy yondashuvlarni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. O'zbekiston maktablarida uy vazifalarini bajarishga bo'lgan motivatsiyaning pastligi va natijada o'quvchilarning o'qish jarayonidagi salohiyatini to'liq ochib berishdagi qiyinchiliklar ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Maqolada, uy vazifalari o'qish jarayonini mustahkamlash, o'quvchilarning mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun qanday qilib samarali ishlatilishi mumkinligi haqida fikrlar bildiriladi. Shuningdek, muallif innovatsion yondashuvlar, jumladan, shaxsiylashtirilgan vazifalar, gamifikatsiya, loyiha asosidagi o'qitish va texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish kabi usullar taklif etiladi.

Maqola o'qituvchilar, ta'lim muassasalari va ota-onalar uchun foydali bo'lib, ular o'quvchilarning uy vazifalariga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish va o'quv jarayonini yanada samarali tashkil etish bo'yicha strategiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *uy vazifasi, motivatsiya, ijodiy yondashuv, o'qitish, o'quvchi.*

“Homework” when this word sounds most people remember their school days usually associated with unpleasant feelings or something difficult to avoid. In fact, homework plays a

crucial role in school education by reinforcing classroom learning and fostering independent study skills. However, motivating school students to consistently complete homework assignments can be a challenge. I have been working as an English teacher for several years and I can say that assigning homework for different grade students has to vary. Since students' ages and abilities are different year by year. In my essay, I am going to explore creative approaches to encourage college, academic lyceum, and high school students to do homework, addressing the problem of low motivation and compliance in terms of Uzbekistan students. Moreover, I would like to find out what types of homework would be more effective for those students.

First of all, let's define homework. What is it and why do we need it?

If we look at the Oxford dictionary homework is “schoolwork that a pupil is required to do at home”. In other words, homework usually refers to academic tasks assigned to students by their teachers that are meant to be completed outside of regular class time. These assignments typically reinforce and extend the learning that has been acquired in the classroom. Homework can include a variety of activities such as reading, writing, problem-solving, research, and project work. Homework serves to reinforce learning, foster independent study skills, prepare for future lessons, extend knowledge, and promote communication and collaboration but its effectiveness depends on various factors and should be balanced to avoid overwhelming students.

Now let's look through some benefits and drawbacks of homework

1. **Reinforce Learning:** Homework provides an opportunity for students to practice and reinforce what they have learned in class. Homework serves as a practice to reinforce classroom learning and helps students understand their strengths and weaknesses (Reese Everett, 2016, p. 12-13). By doing homework students revise what they have learned and develop much more understanding that helps solidify concepts and develop skills through repetition and application.

2. **Independent Learning:** Homework allows students to extend their learning beyond the classroom and practice learning independently (Reese Everett, 2016, p. 6-7). In other words, it encourages students to take responsibility for their own learning. Furthermore, it fosters self-discipline, time management, and the development of independent study skills and also teaches students how to study effectively and develop good study habits (Reese Everett, 2016, p. 8-9).

3. **Extended Learning:** Homework provides an opportunity for students to explore topics not covered in class and utilize resources like the library and the internet (Reese Everett, 2016, p. 7). So, it allows students to delve deeper into a topic, explore additional resources, and engage in critical thinking and creative problem-solving beyond the constraints of classroom time.

4. **Preparation for Assessments:** With homework, students can study and practice the content given in class, helping them to be ready for exams, quizzes, and tests. Teachers can use it as a formative assessment tool to determine what their students have understood.

5. **Parental Involvement:** According to Reese Everett, homework assignments involving student-parent interactions are more likely to be completed. In other words, parents may be able to participate in their child's education through homework. By helping their children with their schoolwork, parents may promote a cooperative learning atmosphere.

Homework can broaden learning, develop autonomous study techniques, encourage critical thinking, and teach students responsibility.

What are the drawbacks of homework?

1. **Time Management Challenges:** When students have many homework assignments from various disciplines, it can increase their workload and perhaps cause time management problems as well as higher levels of stress.

Lack of sleep due to excessive homework can also negatively impact students' focus and overall health (Reese Everett, 2016, p. 22).

2. **Lack of Engagement:** Certain homework assignments may become monotonous or boring for some students, which can sap their enthusiasm and reduce their interest in the material being studied. Reese Everett argues for the effectiveness of homework in improving academic performance, stating that it should only be assigned if it benefits all students equally and helps them succeed.

3. **Inequality and Equity:** Homework can inadvertently contribute to educational inequalities if students do not have equal access to resources, such as a quiet workspace, necessary materials, or parental assistance.

4. **Potential for Burnout:** Excessive homework load or unrealistic expectations can lead to student burnout, affecting their overall well-being and mental health. Additionally, Reese Everett claims that there are various reasons why teachers should not assign homework. He argues that students need free time to relax and engage in activities they enjoy. He suggests that excessive homework prevents students from exploring their interests and pursuing their ideas.

Looking through the above-mentioned advantages and disadvantages of homework it can be concluded that the choice to give homework should be well thought out, taking into account the specific needs and circumstances of each student. Achieving a balance between the advantages of homework and its possible drawbacks is crucial. Assignments should be purposeful, doable, and in line with learning objectives. In my opinion, in our digital age, students need to be assigned homework according to their needs.

Another important issue related to the topic of homework is finding the right type of assignment for students according to their age and needs.

As an English teacher who works in an academic lyceum, I am also concerned about choosing the most effective methods of teaching and learning and assigning proper homework which would be most fruitful. College, lyceum, or high school students often lack motivation to complete homework assignments, leading to incomplete work and missed learning opportunities. In his article titled "Why Do Students Have Difficulties Completing Homework? The Need for Homework Management" by Jianzhong Xu, published in the *Journal of Education and Training Studies* in April 2013, the author explores the challenges students face in completing homework and the importance of homework management. He discusses five major homework challenges, including creating a conducive homework environment, budgeting time, handling distractions, maintaining motivation, and coping with negative emotions. Moreover, the problem stems from various factors such as competing priorities, lack of interest, perceived irrelevance, or overwhelming workloads. This lack of engagement hinders academic progress and inhibits the development of essential skills like responsibility and time management.

To address this problem, several innovative strategies can be implemented:

1. **Relevance and Personalization:** We should design homework assignments that connect with students' interests, goals, and real-world applications. For instance, assigning projects that allow students to explore topics they are passionate about or linking homework to current events can foster intrinsic motivation. As we know students' lives nowadays are closely knit with social media or in other words social networking sites, so we could try giving them homework which can be done by taking short videos or media presentations on these platforms.

2. Gamification: To make our homework assignments more enjoyable and engaging we can integrate game elements into homework. For example, creating a point system, leaderboards, or challenges can encourage friendly competition and provide incentives for completing tasks.

3. Project-Based Learning: One of the most effective homework types is project-based homework assignments that require students to apply their knowledge and skills to real-world problems. It is suggested to assign this type of homework twice or once a month since it requires time to research a topic. This approach promotes critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity, making homework more meaningful and engaging. When applying project-based homework we can assign students to make a presentation, videos, posters, or even take interviews.

4. Technology Integration: To enhance homework engagement we can leverage educational technology tools. Online platforms, interactive websites, or educational apps can provide interactive and personalized learning experiences, making homework tasks more enjoyable and effective. I would like to suggest using educational tools while assigning homework since nearly every student has their own mobile phone and these kinds of apps may be used for free. I have found some of them which are popularly being utilized such as Kahoot, Duolingo, Seesaw, Khan academy and others.

These apps are free to use and have proven their effectiveness showing progress in learners. However, there are some pros and cons of using these kinds of educational apps.

It is worth noting that the pros and cons of homework apps can vary depending on the specific app and individual preferences. Students, parents, and educators need to evaluate the features, usability, and appropriateness of a homework app before incorporating it into their educational routine. To effectively use homework apps for high school students, it's important to choose the right app, set it up properly, utilize reminders and notifications, break tasks into manageable chunks, use available resources, engage in collaboration, avoid distractions, plan, regularly review and update, and protect your privacy and personal information. By following these tips, students can enhance their organization, productivity, and engagement with their homework assignments.

5. Collaborative Homework Tasks: One of the types of homework I would like to implement in Uzbekistan is assigning group projects or collaborative assignments among groups of students not only inside their organization but also to make projects collaborating with other schools and college students. As for now access to the internet and connection is available to everybody. Teachers of the same subjects can create channels in the telegram app that can connect them at once and in those channels, they will decide on projects and create groups of students who will work together on the assigned topic. This fosters peer support, allows for knowledge-sharing, and enhances engagement through social interaction. This kind of activity can be done once a month. Its outcomes will be impressive, I hope.

The target audience for these creative solutions includes high school teachers, administrators, and parents. Teachers can implement these strategies in their classrooms, while administrators can provide professional development opportunities and support the adoption of innovative practices. Parents can play a crucial role by creating a conducive environment and offering support at home.

To implement these creative approaches, collaboration among teachers, administrators, and parents is essential. Professional development workshops can be organized to train teachers on effective implementation strategies. Additionally, ongoing evaluation and feedback should be collected to refine and improve the creative solutions based on students' experiences and outcomes.

The strengths of these creative approaches lie in their potential to enhance student engagement, promote deeper learning, and develop essential skills and these ideas can be implemented in our high schools, colleges, and lyceums. They may make homework more enjoyable and relevant. However, challenges such as resource constraints, resistance to change, and varying levels of technological access among students may limit the widespread implementation of these approaches.

What was Learned about Creativity and Innovation:

Through this project, I have learned that creativity and innovation are vital in addressing educational challenges and our teaching program needs transformations and changes that suit modern standards and development levels. By thinking outside the box and incorporating innovative strategies, we can transform traditional homework practices and create more engaging and effective learning experiences for high school students. This project also highlighted the importance of considering students' needs, interests, and preferences when designing homework assignments.

In conclusion, encouraging high school students to do homework requires creative approaches that foster motivation and engagement. Homework is commonly assigned as a one-size-fits-all task, disregarding students' readiness and learning styles (Dueck, 2014; Eisner, 2003-2004). So, we need some make some changes to improve the quality of homework. By making homework relevant, integrating gamification and technology, promoting project-based learning, and encouraging collaboration, we can overcome the problem of low motivation and compliance. These innovative strategies empower students to take ownership of their learning, deepen their understanding of the subject matter, and develop essential skills for success in high school and beyond. Although there is little consensus on the effects of homework on student learning after a century of research, completion of homework is generally believed to deepen conceptual understanding and lead to greater student achievement (Maltese & Tai, 2012) By embracing creativity and innovation, we can transform homework into a meaningful and enjoyable learning experience.

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